

Supplementary Fig. 3B

PI3K δ i (μ M) PANC-1 MiaPaCa-2
 0 1 3 6 15 0 1 3 6 15

Rabbit monoclonal Anti-Phospho-AKT (Ser473) (D9E) + anti-rabbit HRP (ECL)

Mouse monoclonal Anti-AKT (pan) (40D4) + anti-mouse IRDye 800 CW

Mouse monoclonal Anti- α -tubulin + anti-mouse IRDye 800 CW